

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS: REVIEW OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

The article reviews the international mechanisms of waste management, the implemented administrative-operational models. The study of international experience shows that developed countries have developed not only operational models, but also laws, regulations, environmental standards for the effective management. For Armenia a public-private partnership in the solid waste management will provide efficiency, technical experience and financial investment in the field of waste management. The implementation of separate collection and sorting processes will facilitate recycling and reuse. Meantime, investments in recycling, energy and organic recovery technologies are the fundamentals of the sustainable waste treatment.

Keywords: waste management, public-private, recycling, institutional capacity.

In order to introduce an effective waste management system in the Republic of Armenia, the review of international experience in the implementation of waste management mechanisms is becoming more urgent, ensuring that communities are moving to new creative management mechanisms that enable them to reorganize their management structure and make more productive use of existing resources, attract investments and ensure the security of the population.

All this is argued by a number of interrelated issues, such as the complexity of the urban management process, high environmental requirements, the need to develop a strategy for sustainable community development, the inclusion of long-term extra-budgetary funding in the waste management chain, improving the management system. A significant range of processes, techniques and modeling tools have currently been developed to help solid waste management decision-making[3,4].

From the point of view of the development of the practical directions the theory of waste management, the works of Th. Matheson, M. Medina are very interesting. Matheson's research presents the trends in global MSW, their environmental value, and tax mechanisms that can help reduce waste¹.

Medina, studying the results of waste generation, collection and disposal, states that waste is often not properly collected or disposed by different countries, especially in developing countries. Low-middle-income countries collect 40-60% of community waste, properly remove 5-30 percent, whereas developing countries with high collection rates aim to minimize waste generation and improve recycling².

Because of the stresses of rising waste management's environmental spending, countries are looking for ways to reduce the production and raise the rate of waste recycling. Reducing the waste volume and increasing the recycling rate, in addition to clean environments, guarantee productivity and green jobs³.

Effective waste management is often unavailable, often accounting for 20-50% of community budgets⁴. The smooth running of this vital community service requires integrated systems that are efficient, sustainable and socially secure. Environmental pollution due to improper waste management is considered a global problem.

The world generates 0.74 kg of waste per capita per day, or waste production rates range from 0.11 to 4.54 kg per capita per day. In 2016 about 2.1 billion tons of garbage was created, the volume of which, according to

¹ Th. Matheson, "Disposal is Not Free: Fiscal Instruments to Internalize the Environmental Costs of Solid Waste." IMF Working Paper, 2019.

² Medina, M. (2010), "Solid Wastes, Poverty and the Environment in Developing Country Cities: Challenges and Opportunities," World Institute for Development Economics Research, WP No. 2010.23.

³ European Commission (2015). "Closing the Loop – an EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy", COM (2015) 614, Brussels, February 12.

⁴ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/brief/solid-waste-management> Solid Waste Management September 23, 2019

forecasts, in 2050 will amount to 3.4 billion⁵. Almost half of the gross solid waste is generated at the expense of developing countries. However, high-income countries produce almost twice as much waste per capita. In high-income countries, not only goods but also cars, machinery and electrical equipment are consumed. Internationally, the largest category of waste is food waste - biological waste, which accounts for 44% of world waste, and dry recyclable waste (plastic, paper - cardboard, metal, glass) - 38%. Studies show that the composition of waste varies considerably from country to country. In high-income countries, solid waste contains more paper, plastic than in low-income countries.

Waste management is a powerful community service, for the implementation of which different administrative-operational models are used. Developed countries develop laws, regulations, targets, and environmental standards for the effective management. This process is difficult to manage in low- and middle-income countries, where the problems are not limited to the lack of institutional planning and management capacity, but there is a lack of funding.

Particularly in the developing world, local governments frequently lack sufficient resources to provide adequate waste management. For all these reasons, waste management is a macro-relevant issue which needs a development of a policy framework for local governments to improve waste management. The choice of waste management method largely depends on economic factors.

Cost benchmarking allows to identify optimization options by comparing cost structure and data. Expenditure figures typically include the cost of waste management, disposal services, and revenue from the sale of waste for recycling. Comprehensive analysis includes waste collection, treatment (sorting, recovery, recycling, etc.) costs, including closed landfill management, personnel costs, and all other costs related to waste management. Cost comparison can be used to evaluate existing inefficient waste management systems to move to a more efficient system.

The purpose of the pay-as-you-throw mechanism is to introduce the "polluter pays" principle, so that garbage collection fees are collected from producers based on the amount of waste generated by them. In practice, the system can be implemented in different ways, in particular: volume schemes (bin size selection); bag-based schemes (number of waste bags used); weight schemes (weight of waste collected in a container or container); frequency circuits (the frequency with which the container / container is removed), this approach can also be combined with volume-weight circuits) [1,5].

Waste management contracts based on operating results are mechanisms for local governments that contract with private providers of waste management certain services. It facilitates the introduction of the best environmental management methods.

Governments and waste management companies consider awareness to be very important. A special way to raise awareness is to set up a network of waste consultants.

Public-private partnership is a source of efficiency, technical experience and financial investment in the waste management. As costs cannot be entirely covered by fees received from customers, it is more widespread to call on particular service providers (for the collection of waste, the running of a waste transfer plant or a technical landfill center) than to nominate a large-scale private operator covering all fields of experience, operational skills and versatility. Yet the presence of the private sector alone won't solve all the problems. While the public sector is far from abrogating its obligations, it must reinforce its responsibilities.

Recent trends in private sector participation in municipal solid waste in developing countries are attributed in part to more stringent environmental requirements, acknowledging that the private sector can play an important role in improving solid waste collection, disposal and environmental issues. They include regulation of waste collection initiatives as an option for public-private partnership; implementation and promotion contracts based on greater results for street cleaning and collection of solid waste; involvement of the private sector in cleaning and utilization projects to implement innovation in waste management, recycling and energy programs; as well as involvement of the private sector in financing capital investments.

Different waste management schemes are implemented in the EU member states. Thus, in Germany and Italy community waste collection is carried out through the direct provision of services or by a community managed company. In Poland, Romania, Sweden is implemented waste collection and transportation services outsourcing by a private operator. [2,4].

In general, the share of the private sector in European countries is higher in the collection and transportation services than in the recycling phase. The table below shows the structure of public-private sector participation in waste management. International Community Service Research Center (PSIRU) in the study of public-private notes that the implementation of community services by the private sector is less costly than by the public sector^{6,7}.

⁵ S.Kaza, L.Yao, What a waste 2.0. A Global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050. 2018 International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank

⁶ PSIRU (2012) Public and Private Sector Efficiency. Available at: <http://www.psiru.org/sites/default/files/2014-07-EWGHTEfficiency.pdf>

⁷ Bel, G./Fageda, X. and Warner, M. (2010) Is private production of public services cheaper than public production? A meta-regression analysis of solid waste and water services. P. 575. Available at: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pam.20509/full>

Table 1

Share of services provided in several EU countries by type of operator⁸

	Private	Public	Mixed
Germany	50%	45%	5%
Italia	27%	55%	18%
Poland			
Romania	53,7%	46,3%	-
Spain	collection 80%	collection 20%	4%
	Recycling 80%	Recycling 20%	
Sweden	collection 71%	collection 40%	
	Recycling <90%	Recycling >10%	

Public-private partnership is a source of efficiency, technical experience and financial investment in the field of waste management. During the last 25 years, huge changes have taken place in the field of community waste management: significantly has been reduced production of unsorted residual waste due to sorting, such as paper, glass and plastic. In addition, organic waste collection models have been introduced to address both the recovery of nutrients from organic waste and the prevention of emissions during landfilling.

Solid waste management is a powerful community service, for the implementation of which different administrative-operational models are used. Developed countries develop laws, regulations, targets, and environmental standards for the effective solid waste management. This process is difficult to manage in low- and middle-income countries, where the problems are not limited to the lack of institutional planning and management capacity, but there is a lack of funding. The following issues can be highlighted in the waste management process in developing countries: lack of funding for waste collection, transportation and disposal systems, the complexity of decentralized management and design, the lack of opportunities to increase coverage of reducing environmental impact; lack of institutional capacity for planning, monitoring, implementation, etc [1,6].

The lack of financial resources to cope with the rising amount of waste generated by rapidly growing cities is one of the key factors. Insufficient fees paid and insufficient funds from municipal budgets are unable to fund sufficient financing of needed service levels.

As we have already mentioned, garbage collection is the main service provided at the community level. Garbage collection weights vary according to the level of development of the countries. Thus, in high-income countries, the rate is 100%, in the middle - 51%, in the low - 39%. In low-income countries, uncollected waste is managed by households (burial, incineration, etc.). At the same time, the level of garbage collection is higher in cities than in villages⁹.

Although garbage collection rates are very different, the community garbage collection and recycling systems of many developing countries are

inadequate. Most municipal waste is disposed of in sanitary or poorly controlled landfills.

In the waste management system are also important pricing modes, which can significantly increase the amount of income. In low-income countries, garbage collection fees are fixed per household, while volume-based fees are more common in developed countries. Fees charged by commercial organizations vary mainly according to the tonnage produced, while in middle-income countries the fees are uniform for easy administration and collection.

In Armenia there is a need to implement for integrated management of municipal solid waste. Linking private and public actions can strengthen waste management services and ensure a proper framework. The efficiency of facility growth, infrastructure management, waste recycling can increasingly raise as a result of joint actions. The evidence shows that no ordinary model is effective in all developing countries. It also relates closely to individuals via waste generation and is related to lifestyles and patterns of resources use. In all stages of a solid waste management the relationship between people in their engagement and empowerment is important. In addition, social recognition, affordability and willingness to pay are additional factors that need to be created and organized.

The implementation of separate collection and sorting processes to facilitate recycling and reuse, the organization of waste transport, and investments in recycling, energy and organic recovery technologies are the fundamentals of the sustainable waste treatment. It should be possible for public authorities to give the private sector a transparent, well-defined and protected contractual structure. Public-private contracts must be reasonably long-term in order to allow private operators to customize and enhance the provision of services and to comply with municipal budgets. The private sector's mobilization, does not itself constitute a solution to better waste management. A waste management system must be supported by better funding structures, enhanced technological and administrative capacities on the part of public authorities and a well-structured regulatory framework in order to be effective and acceptable.

⁸ PSIRU (2012) Public and Private Sector Efficiency. Available at: <http://www.psir.org/sites/default/files/2014-07-EWGHTEfficiency.pdf>

⁹ S.Kaza, L.Yao, What a waste 2.0. A Global snapshot of solid waste management to 2050. 2018 International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank

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